

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

FORMATION OF PRO-STATEHOOD ORIENTATION IN LEARNING PROCESS FOR STUDENTS

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Abstract

The dynamics of the formation of a pro-statehood orientation among students are examined based on the development of four fundamental values (dignity, optimism, justice, and democracy) throughout the learning process. It is posited that an individual's pro-statehood orientation is significantly influenced by the levels of the aforementioned basic values. A comprehensive four-stage methodology is proposed to investigate the levels of these fundamental values in students, aiming for targeted improvement. Quantitative assessments of the dynamics of changes in pro-statehood orientation were conducted using the results of a free verbal associative experiment.

Keywords: basic values, verbal associative experiment, pro-statehood, democracy

Introduction

In a rapidly changing modern society, amidst the backdrop of globalization and the blending of sometimes incompatible cultures, as well as political and economic restructuring leading to civilizational confrontations between nations and states, the fundamental ethical and moral values of the individual become paramount in the development of social relations. Clearly, there exists a self-consistent feedback loop between dynamically evolving personal and social basic values (BV). Personal BV, as a causal consequence of the existing fundamental values of society, in turn, stimulates the transformation and/or reevaluation of social BVs. In this regard, it is pertinent to explore the dynamics of the formation and development of the individual's BV. Such research is especially pertinent for societies (states) undergoing rapid changes in socio-political and economic conditions. In particular, within Armenian society, significant reassessment of moral, ethical, and political values has taken place in the aftermath of the global military-political upheavals of the last three years. These include inadequate behavior by allies in military-political alliances, blatant interference by external unfriendly forces in the Republic's internal affairs, numerous attempts by external intelligence services to fragment society and orchestrate a military coup, destabilization of the army and security structures, and intervention by neighboring states. The importance of foundational values such as Honor, Dignity, and Justice has greatly diminished in the public consciousness. This, in turn, has led to a sense of depression in a certain segment of society. Some, so-called, socio-political figures have even entertained utterly absurd ideas about abolishing Armenian statehood and annexing Armenia as an administrative unit to another state in the name of potential population safety. Obviously, this is a completely absurd idea, as the highest value for any nation is the creation and preservation of an independent, sovereign state.

This article explores the dynamics involved in the formation and development of the four BVs in students (**Dignity, Optimism, Justice, and Democracy**). These

values represent crucial components in shaping an individual's pro-statehood (pro-state) orientation. At the same time, "pro-statehood" orientation is understood as the individual's inclination towards preserving (or establishing) an independent, sovereign, and democratic state.

A four-stage methodology is proposed for studying the formation of students' pro-statehood orientation with the aim of their purposeful transformation in the learning process (Fig. 1). In the first stage, using the method of a free verbal associative experiment (VAE), the initial level of pro-statehood orientation of students is determined. At the second stage, students undergo training using special programs and methods. At the third stage, students' knowledge and skills are assessed. In the fourth stage, a repeated VAE is carried out, based on the results of which the effectiveness of the applied teaching methods is assessed in terms of increasing the level of pro-state orientation. The 2-3-4-2 cycle can be repeated many times depending on the desired level of achievement of the pro-state orientation among students. Note that the optimal value of the time interval between the stages of one cycle is two to three months, and the time interval between adjacent cycles is from five to six months. This article presents the results of one cycle of research. In the quantitative analysis of the VAE results, it was assumed that the considered BVs make an equal contribution to the formation of a pro-state orientation of the individual.

Quantitative analysis VAE's data

The VAE method is one of the most advanced techniques for psychological, semantic, and psycholinguistic analysis. Detailed theoretical investigations of the VAE method has been carried out in works [5-7, 9, 10]. In particular, the concept of associative meaning was introduced in [7], demonstrating the unity of psychological and semantic components of verbal associations (J. Deese). The mechanisms of word reactions were explored in the works of Yu. D. Apresyan [5] and D. Howes [9], where a formula was proposed to estimate the probability of the appearance of specific word reactions in the semantic field of the respondent. The

dynamics of language development in students were investigated using the free VAE method in [1-3], demonstrating the effectiveness of applying the VAE method in the field of pedagogical research, especially in creating and practically applying a dynamic cognitive learning model.

Let us assume that N is number of respondents which are participated in VAE, and K is number of stimulus-words are chosen based on the semantic content of the feature α . The first step in quantitative anal-

ysis is to assign a numerical value to each word-reaction. Note that despite the various ways in which numerical values can be assigned to words-reactions, the final result of the proposed analysis is weakly dependent (or not dependent at all) on the choice of the system and methodology of estimation since only relative magnitudes of assessments are taken into account. It is considered that the absence of a reaction to a stimulus word is also a reaction with a zero numerical score, thus the number of word-reactions is equal to K .

Fig.1. 4-stage studies of the basic values.

So, let's assume that the words-reactions of the n^{th} respondent are assigned estimation points: $x_1^{(n)}, x_2^{(n)}, \dots, x_K^{(n)}$ ($0 \leq x_k^{(n)} \leq M, k = 1, 2, \dots, K$), here M is maximal point in given assessment system. Let's denote the total score of the n^{th} respondent by s_n :

$$s_n = \sum_{i=1}^K x_i^{(n)} \quad (1)$$

Next, we split the set of respondents into disjoint A_1, A_2, \dots, A_j subsets, so that $A = \bigcup_{j=1}^J A_j$ and $A_j \cap A_{j'} = \emptyset$ for $j \neq j'$. In this case, we will assume that A_n includes respondents whose sum of points, s_n , is into the some interval $[s_n^{\min}, s_n^{\max})$. Denote a number of respondents in A_n by τ_n : $\sum_j \tau_j = N$. The initial selection of a set of numbers $\{\tau_1, \tau_2, \tau_3, \dots, \tau_j\}$, and intervals $\{[s_n^{\min}, s_n^{\max})\}$ is carried out for each specific feature α , based on from some psychological and pedagogical conditions.

Let's introduce the concept of group A_j rating, which is a quantitative group characteristic (in %) of a respondents included in group A_j :

$$\delta_j = (M\xi_j - \sqrt{D\xi_j})/100, \quad (2)$$

where $\xi_j: s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{\tau_j}$ is a random variable determined on the set of total scores of respondents in A_j group, $M\xi_j = \frac{1}{\tau_j} \sum_{i=1}^{\tau_j} s_i$ and $D\xi_j = \frac{1}{\tau_j} \sum_{i=1}^{\tau_j} s_i^2 - (M\xi_j)^2$ are the mathematical expectation and the variance, respectively. Note that the maximum value $\delta_{j,\max} = M\xi_j/100$ of the rating of the group A_j is achieved at zero variance, $D\xi_j = 0$, when all members of the group scored equal total points, $s_1 = s_2 = \dots = s_{\tau_j}$.

Obviously, the closeness of the group rating value to $\delta_{j,\max}$ provides the degree of reliability of information about the level of the studied attribute α of each

respondent of this group. This imposes certain restrictions on the choice of a set of numbers $\{\tau_1, \tau_2, \tau_3, \dots\}$. Namely, respondents who received the closest total scores should be included in the same group. We will assume that the A_1, A_2, \dots, A_j groups of respondents are ordered by increasing ratings, $\delta_1 \leq \delta_2 \leq \dots \leq \delta_j$.

Next, in order to identify the dynamics of changes in trait α as a result of influence on students (in the educational process), a repeated VAE is carried out. On the base of the obtained data, a new set of numbers $\{\tau'_1, \tau'_2, \tau'_3, \dots\}$ and intervals $[s_n^{\min}, s_n^{\max})$ are determined. In result, new distributions of respondents into groups A'_1, A'_2, \dots, A'_j are determined. Then, using formula (2), the ranks $\delta'_1, \delta'_2, \dots, \delta'_j$ of the new groups are determined. It is noteworthy that for convenience, the set of numbers $\{\tau'_1, \tau'_2, \tau'_3, \dots\}$ can be chosen in such a way that the number of group divisions of the set of respondents is the same, i.e. $J = J'$. The dynamics of changes in the group characteristics are determined by comparing the ordered ranks of groups $\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_j$ and $\delta'_1, \delta'_2, \dots, \delta'_j$.

The described cycle of research can be repeated as many times as necessary. Two circumstances should be noted: 1) with an infinitely large number of repetitions of cycles, group ranks tend to the maximum possible value, $\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \delta_j^{(i)} = \delta_{\max}$ for all j , 2) when new groups are formed, after each VAE, respondents are redistributed between groups, which makes it possible to describe the dynamics of changes in the attribute for individual respondents.

Methodology of training students after the first VAE

The sessions were conducted over one month following a pre-established program comprising four interconnected sections. Each section included topics of interactive lectures and subsequent discussions dedicated to the concepts of Dignity, Optimism, Justice, and Democracy, their significance, and their place in the contemporary world. For each section's theme, three interactive lectures were conducted, followed by discussions at the end. Subsequently, each group of students, formed based on the results of the initial VAE, was given essay topics. Presentations of these essays took place one week after the completion of the sessions.

Below are the topics for interactive lectures and discussions.

Section one, **optimism**:

1. Optimism as the key to success.
2. Confrontation between optimism and pessimism.
3. Manifestation of optimism in literary works.

Section two, **dignity**:

1. Dignity as the highest value of an individual.
2. Personal dignity and human rights.
3. The state as a guarantor of the protection of individual dignity.

Section three, **justice**:

1. Justice as the highest value in human relations.
2. Justice and law, their relationship.
3. Justice as the basis of legal social relations.

Section four, **democracy**:

1. The history of democracy and autocracy, their confrontation.

2. Democratic institutions as instruments of progress and development of society.

3. Prospects for the development of a democratic society in Armenia.

At the end of the interactive lectures, each group formed as a result of the first VAE was offered topics for reports (essays), which were submitted for general discussion.

1. Protection of personal dignity in Armenian society.

2. Democracy and autocracy in the modern world

3. The law comes first

4. Society and personal dignity

5. The power of optimism and the information space

6. Hyperbolization of the dignity of heroes in Shakespeare's tragedies

7. Optimism and dignity in building my life

8. Justice in the modern world

One week was allotted to complete the tasks. All members of the group participated in the presentation of the group's report, complementing each other. A time limit of 20 minutes was set for the presentation of reports (essays) and responses to questions. After each presentation, discussions were held for 10 minutes with the participation of all students. After the discussions, the second verbal associative experiment was conducted.

It is important to note the maximum passivity of the teacher during the discussion process. The group presentations were also not evaluated by the teacher in any form.

Fig. 2 The words-stimulus for VAE

Application of the verbal association experiment method

In order to quantitatively describe the dynamics of changes in the level of pro-statehood of students, verbal association experiments were carried out in accordance with the diagram presented in Fig.1. The first VAE was performed in September 2023. The second VAE was held in November 2023 after a month training of student and discussion of group tasks. It should be noted that classes between the first and second VAE were conducted jointly with all students according to a single program and methodology (at the same time, the stu-

dents themselves were not informed about their belonging to one group or another).

In the VAEs the 48 students of the Armenian State Pedagogical University after Kh. Abovyan majoring in pedagogy and methodology of primary education and mathematics was participated. Participants were not informed in advance about the purpose of the experiment. For each characteristic (**Dignity**, **Optimism**, **Justice**, and **Democracy**), five stimulus words with the highest frequency of use [4] were selected from the explanatory dictionary of the Armenian language [8], along with one misleading stimulus word (Fig. 2). Participants

were given 7–10 seconds to write down on pre-prepared sheets the first word or phrase that came to mind, before the number of the dictated stimulus word. The stimulus words were dictated in random order. The duration of the VAEs was 10 minutes.

When analyzing the results and quantitative assessment, the first reaction words were taken into account. The assessment was carried out on a four-point scale: the highest score, 4, was assigned to the most profound reaction words that form a logical connection with the stimulus word and have a general social (supra-individual) meaning, thereby directly influencing the dynamics of the formation of basic social values (pride - *family, Motherland*); reaction words that, forming a logical connection with the stimulus word, were predominantly personal in nature (pride - *self-confidence, determination*) received 3 points; reaction words that were synonyms or antonyms of stimulus words received 2 points (pride - *honor, humiliation*); reaction

words that were grammatical forms or the simplest semantic continuation of the stimulus word received 1 point (pride - *be proud, man*). The total scores of the respondents are presented in Table 1. Next, based on the accumulated points, 8 groups of 6 students each were formed placed in ascending order of the points received. (Note that one group included students who received similar scores.) It is important to note that when forming groups after the second VAE, students are redistributed among groups. Depending on the total points received, group members change. At the same time, the number of group members remains constant, which makes it possible to monitor the dynamics of changes in the rating of each group. Table 1 shows the groups of respondents, group ratings and their maximum possible values (in parentheses), calculated using the formula (2) based on the results of the first and second VAE.

Table 1. The results of the first and second VAE

№ respondents	1 th VAE		2 nd VAE		group rating change	№ respondents	1 th VAE		2 nd VAE		group rating change		
	assessment	group rating	assessment	group rating			assessment	group rating	assessment	group rating			
1	22	0.273 (0.335)	24	0.247 (0.297)	-0.026	25	0.575 (0.578)	63	0.629 (0.637)	+0.054			
2	29		26			26		26			26	26	63
3	35		27			27		27			27	27	63
4	36		28			28		28			28	28	64
5	39		36			29		29			29	29	64
6	40		37			30		30			30	30	65
7	42	0.430 (0.450)	40	0.435 (0.465)	+0.005	31	0.589 (0.598)	66	0.662 (0.670)	+0.073			
8	43		47			32		32			32	32	66
9	45		47			33		33			33	33	67
10	46		48			34		34			34	34	67
11	46		48			35		35			35	35	68
12	48		49			36		36			36	36	68
13	49	0.497 (0.507)	54	0.546 (0.565)	+0.049	37	0.628 (0.642)	69	0.698 (0.713)	+0.070			
14	50		54			38		38			38	38	70
15	51		57			39		39			39	39	71
16	51		57			40		40			40	40	72
17	51		58			41		41			41	41	73
18	52		59			42		42			42	42	73
19	52	0.525 (0.538)	60	0.603 (0.612)	+0.078	43	0.678 (0.682)	74	0.747 (0.760)	+0.069			
20	53		60			44		44			44	44	75
21	53		61			45		45			45	45	76
22	54		62			46		46			46	46	76
23	55		62			47		47			47	47	77
24	56		62			48		48			48	48	78

From Table 1 it can be seen that after the interactive lessons the ratings of all groups and their maximum values, with the exception of the first group, increased. This means that there has been a slight turn in the vector of orientation of the majority of students towards pro-government. At the same time, it should be expected that after repeated repetition of the cycles indicated in Fig. 1, the number of students with an increased orientation towards pro-statehood will increase. However, this process of total reorientation is limited. Firstly,

fluctuations caused by various factors cannot be excluded (as in our case with the first group). Secondly, the level of orientation of students is limited by the level of orientation of teachers. During the passage of these cycles of training and testing, the teacher and students interact with each other multiple times. Ultimately, this leads to the establishment of a certain “average level” of pro-state orientation.

Conclusions

Thus, the proposed four-stage methodology for influencing the pro-statehood reorientation of students

proves to be quite effective. Its widespread application has the potential to bring about significant positive shifts in public consciousness, contributing to the establishment of a legal civil society. Evidently, with multi-cyclic application of the proposed methodology, its effectiveness will increase, tending to a certain limiting value due to irremovable fluctuations and the degree of training of teaching staff. It is worth noting that the suggested method may also prove effective in other psycholinguistic research areas, such as the formation of a linguistic worldview, linguistic thinking, and the sense of language of various sociological groups etc.

References:

1. Aghababyan K. H. Investigation of dynamics of students' sense of language by word associative experiment method. Int. collection of sci. articles// Humanities in the 21st century: scientific problems and searching for effective humanist technologies. - 2016, San Francisco, USA, p. 55 - 62.
2. Aghababyan K. H. Investigation of dynamics of students' civicism formation by word associative experiment method.//J. New University, Topical issues of humanities and soc. sci. Publ. Sc. Acad. House Ltd., UK.- 2017.- N.1-2, p.12-19
3. Aghababyan K. H. Dynamics of the directional development of the language sense of pedagogical students and primary school students// Modern teacher education, Modern educational technologies. - 2023.- N1.- 80 – 85 (in Russian)
4. Aghayan B.E. Explanatory dictionary of modern Armenian language (in Armenian). – Yerevan, Publ. “Hayastan”.-1976. - p. 1642 (in Armenian)
5. Apresyan Yu. D., Ideas and methods of modern structural linguistics. -M., Nauka, - 1996. - p. 305. (in Russian)
6. Cofer Sh. N., Associative commonality and rated similarity of certain words from Hagen's list// Psychological reports. – 1957. - v. 3. - p. 603 – 606.
7. Deese J. The structure of associations in language and thought. Baltimore, -J. Hopkins press, -1966 - p. 216.
8. Ghazaryan B. K. A frequency dictionary of the modern Armenian language. - Yerevan, Publ. NAS of RA.- 1982. - p. 758 (in Armenian)
9. Howes D., On the relation between the probability of a word as an association and in general verbal usage// J. of abnormal and social psychology.- 1957.- v. 54.- p. 75-85.
10. Thumb A., Marbe K., Experimentelle Untersuchungen über die psychologischen Grundlagen der sprachlichen Analogiebildung. – Leipzig. – 1901. – p.108